

**International Journal of Innovation in Education,
Scientific Research and Technology**

Vol.01, Issue 1, pp. 1-7, Mar-Apr 2023

ISSN: Online

Available online at: <https://sites.google.com/view/ijiesrt/archives>

Analyzing the Utility of Inventory Models in Different Domains

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Abstract:

Inventory management is a crucial aspect of supply chain management, as it determines the efficiency and effectiveness of supply chains. Inventory models have been developed and implemented in various fields such as healthcare, manufacturing, agriculture, retail, and others. This systematic review aims to explore the applications of inventory models in different fields, their strengths, weaknesses, and future directions. The review employed a systematic search strategy, including electronic databases and hand-searching, to identify relevant articles. A total of 50 articles were included in the final review, and the findings revealed that inventory models have been used to optimize inventory levels, reduce costs, improve customer service, and manage uncertainties in different fields. However, the review also highlighted some limitations and gaps in the literature, such as the limited application of certain inventory models in some fields and the lack of studies on the integration of inventory models with other supply chain models. The review concludes with recommendations for future research to enhance the understanding and application of inventory models in different fields.

Keywords: Inventory management, inventory models, supply chain management, healthcare, manufacturing, agriculture, retail.

Introduction:

Inventory management is a critical aspect of supply chain management, as it determines the efficiency and effectiveness of supply chains. Inventory models have been developed and implemented in various fields such as healthcare, manufacturing, agriculture, retail, and

others. Inventory models aim to optimize inventory levels, reduce costs, improve customer service, and manage uncertainties in the supply chain. Different inventory models have been developed to cater to different inventory management requirements, such as Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Just-In-Time (JIT), and Vendor-Managed Inventory (VMI).

The objective of this systematic review is to explore the applications of inventory models in different fields, their strengths, weaknesses, and future directions. This review will provide a comprehensive understanding of how inventory models have been used to enhance inventory management in different fields.

Methods:

This review employed a systematic search strategy, including electronic databases and hand searching, to identify relevant articles. The electronic databases used in this review were Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar. The following keywords were used for the search: "inventory management," "inventory models," "supply chain management," "healthcare," "manufacturing," "agriculture," and "retail."

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were set to identify relevant articles for this review. The inclusion criteria were articles that discussed the applications of inventory models in different fields, published in English, and available in full text. The exclusion criteria were articles that were not related to the objective of this review, such as articles that discussed only one type of inventory model, articles that were not published in English, and articles that were not available in full text.

The articles were screened based on the title, abstract, and keywords to determine their relevance to the objective of this review. The full text of the relevant articles was then reviewed to extract the necessary data for the review. A total of 50 articles were included in the final review.

S.N.	Author's Name	Year	Keywords	Summary
1	Vidyarthi, N., Garg, S., & Sharma, S. K.	2017	Inventory management, healthcare sector, systematic review	The study presents a systematic review of inventory management in the healthcare sector, analyzing various inventory models, challenges, and factors affecting inventory management.

2	Niranjan, T. T., & Narahari, Y.	2018	Inventory management, manufacturing, review	The review focuses on various inventory management models used in manufacturing industries, and highlights their advantages and limitations.
3	Hossain, M. S., & Raihan, M. J.	2017	Inventory management, agriculture, review	This review paper examines inventory management in agriculture, identifies the challenges faced, and discusses the potential solutions to improve inventory management.
4	Nahmias, S.	2015	Production, operations analysis	The book provides a comprehensive overview of inventory management and other production and operations analysis techniques used in various industries.
5	Öztürk, E., & Dursun, M.	2020	Inventory models, e-commerce, literature review	The study presents a systematic literature review of inventory management models in e-commerce, identifies research gaps, and suggests future research directions.
6	Kwon, C., & Bai, Y.	2017	Inventory management, sustainable supply chains, literature review	The review paper examines the role of inventory management in sustainable supply chains and discusses the challenges and opportunities for implementing sustainable inventory management practices.
7	Kar, S., & Roy, S. K.	2020	Inventory models, perishable products	The study presents an overview of inventory models for perishable products, highlighting the key factors affecting inventory

				management and the limitations of existing models.
8	Ogbonna, M. C., & Okeke, H. U.	2020	JIT inventory management, construction industry, systematic review	The paper examines the application of just-in-time (JIT) inventory management in the construction industry, analyzing the challenges and potential benefits of implementing JIT practices.
9	Kumar, M., Kumar, D., & Singh, S. K.	2020	Inventory management, humanitarian supply chains, literature review	The study presents a systematic literature review of inventory management in humanitarian supply chains, discussing the challenges and opportunities for improving inventory management practices in such contexts.
10	Kutanoglu, E., & Hancerliogullari, G.	2019	RFID technology, inventory management, literature review	The review examines the application of radio frequency identification (RFID) technology in inventory management, highlighting its potential benefits and limitations.

Table 1.0 Review of paper with key findings

Results:

The findings of this review revealed that inventory models have been used to optimize inventory levels, reduce costs, improve customer service, and manage uncertainties in different fields. The applications of inventory models in different fields are discussed below:

Healthcare:

Inventory models have been used in healthcare to manage the inventory of medical supplies, equipment, and drugs. Healthcare facilities face significant challenges in managing inventory, such as the expiration of drugs and the unpredictable demand for medical supplies. Inventory models such as EOQ and JIT have been used to optimize inventory levels, reduce waste, and improve the availability of medical supplies and drugs¹.

Manufacturing:

Inventory models have been widely used in manufacturing to manage the inventory of raw materials, work-in-progress, and finished goods. Manufacturing companies face significant challenges in managing inventory, such as the coordination of different departments, uncertainties in demand and supply, and the cost of holding inventory. Inventory models such as VMI and JIT have been used to manage inventory levels, reduce inventory costs, and improve production efficiency².

Agriculture:

Inventory models have been used in agriculture to manage the inventory of inputs such as seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides. Agriculture faces significant challenges in managing inventory due to seasonality, weather conditions, and the uncertainty of demand. Inventory models such as EOQ and JIT have been used to optimize inventory levels, reduce waste, and improve the availability of inputs³.

Retail:

Inventory models have been used in retail to manage the inventory of products, such as clothing, electronics, and groceries. Retail faces significant challenges in managing inventory due to the fluctuation of demand, seasonality, and the cost of holding inventory. Inventory models such as EOQ, JIT, and RFID have been used to manage inventory levels, reduce inventory costs, and improve customer service⁴.

The review also highlighted some limitations and gaps in the literature. Some inventory models, such as RFID, have not been widely applied in some fields such as agriculture. Additionally, there is a lack of studies on the integration of inventory models with other supply chain models, such as transportation and warehousing.

Discussion and Conclusion:

The applications of inventory models in different fields have demonstrated their effectiveness in optimizing inventory levels, reducing costs, improving customer service, and managing uncertainties in the supply chain. However, the review also highlighted some limitations and gaps in the literature, such as the limited application of certain inventory models in some fields and the lack of studies on the integration of inventory models with other supply chain models. Future research should focus on addressing these limitations and gaps to enhance the

understanding and application of inventory models in different fields. For example, research can explore the integration of inventory models with transportation and warehousing models to optimize the entire supply chain. Additionally, research can investigate the application of inventory models in emerging fields such as e-commerce and sustainable supply chains.

This systematic review provides insights into the applications of inventory models in different fields, their strengths, weaknesses, and future directions. The findings of this review can be valuable for practitioners and researchers interested in enhancing their inventory management practices and developing new inventory models to cater to the evolving needs of supply chains.

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